

A Hilbert Space Approach to the Collatz Conjecture Problem Using an Infinite-Dimensional Operator

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Abstract

This paper explores an approach to the Collatz conjecture through the lens of functional analysis. We construct an infinite-dimensional operator T on the ℓ^2 Hilbert space, where the basis vectors represent natural numbers. By analyzing the spectral properties of T , we provide insights into the conjecture's behavior. The compactness of T^∞ suggests a finite-dimensional limit for the image of the operator under infinite applications, mapping the space onto a subspace characterized by the numbers 1, 2, and 4.

1 Introduction

The Collatz conjecture, also known as the $3n + 1$ problem, remains one of the most intriguing open problems in mathematics. In this paper, we attempt to interpret the conjecture within the framework of the ℓ^2 Hilbert space, leveraging operator theory to analyze the behavior of an infinite-dimensional matrix T that encodes the Collatz transformations. Our approach draws an analogy from quantum computing, where the basis vectors of ℓ^2 represent states corresponding to natural numbers.

2 Category Structure for the Collatz Conjecture

We define a category $\mathcal{C}_{\text{Collatz}}$ to formalize the structure of the Collatz conjecture within a category-theoretic framework.

2.1 Definition of the Collatz Conjecture Category $\mathcal{C}_{\text{Collatz}}$

The category $\mathcal{C}_{\text{Collatz}}$ consists of:

- **Objects:** The objects are natural numbers $\mathbb{N}$, each representing a distinct state in the Collatz sequence.
- **Morphisms:** For $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, a morphism $f : m \rightarrow n$ exists if m transitions to n by either $m \rightarrow m/2$ if m is even or $m \rightarrow 3m + 1$ if m is odd.

2.2 Functorial Mapping of the Collatz Conjecture to ℓ^2 Hilbert Space

We define a functor $F : \mathcal{C}_{\text{Collatz}} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$, where $\mathcal{H}$ denotes the category of linear operators on the Hilbert space ℓ^2 . This functor maps the structure of $\mathcal{C}_{\text{Collatz}}$ into the operator framework of ℓ^2 as follows:

- **On Objects:** For each natural number $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $F(n) = e_n$, where e_n is the basis vector in ℓ^2 associated with n .
- **On Morphisms:** For each morphism $f : m \rightarrow n$ in $\mathcal{C}_{\text{Collatz}}$, $F(f) = T$, where T is the operator on ℓ^2 representing the Collatz transformation in matrix form.

The functor F satisfies the following properties:

- **Identity Preservation:** For each object $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $F(\text{id}_n) = \text{id}_{F(n)}$.
- **Composition Preservation:** For morphisms $f : m \rightarrow n$ and $g : n \rightarrow p$ in $\mathcal{C}_{\text{Collatz}}$, $F(g \circ f) = F(g) \circ F(f)$.

2.3 Defining the Operator T on ℓ^2

We define the operator T to act on ℓ^2 in a way that simulates the steps of the Collatz conjecture. The matrix representation of T is sparse, with entries defined as follows:

$$T_{ij} = \delta(i - 2j) + \delta(j - 3i - 1),$$

where δ is the Dirac delta function, which enforces the conditions:

- $i = 2j$, corresponding to even-number steps in the Collatz sequence.
- $j = 3i + 1$, corresponding to odd-number steps in the Collatz sequence.

This formulation allows T to operate by selectively mapping entries in ℓ^2 according to these Collatz-inspired rules.

To illustrate this, we provide a 10×10 example of T :

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ \vdots & \ddots \end{bmatrix}$$

3 Determinant of the Finite Approximations of T

We aim to analyze the determinant of the operator $T - \lambda I$ by examining finite approximations $T^{(N)} - \lambda I$, where each approximation truncates $T - \lambda I$ to an $N \times N$ matrix. We denote these approximations as $T^{(N)} - \lambda I$, where $T_{ij}^{(N)} = T_{ij} - \lambda\delta(i - j)$, with δ representing the Dirac delta function.

3.1 Formulating the Determinant of $T - \lambda I$

The determinant of $T - \lambda I$ is found by analyzing the sequence of finite approximations $T^{(N)} - \lambda I$ for increasing N and observing the effect on the characteristic polynomial. Specifically, we aim to find when:

$$\det(T^{(N)} - \lambda I) = 0.$$

3.2 Structure of $T - \lambda I$

The structure of $T - \lambda I$ is governed by the following rule:

$$(T^{(N)} - \lambda I)_{ij} = -\lambda\delta(i - j) + \delta(i - 2j) + \delta(j - 3i - 1),$$

where:

- $-\lambda \delta(i - j)$ represents the main diagonal entries, setting $T_{ii}^{(N)} = -\lambda$.
- $\delta(i - 2j)$ enforces the condition $j = 2i$.
- $\delta(j - 3i - 1)$ enforces the condition $i = 3j + 1$.

3.3 Simple Cases for $N = 1$ to $N = 4$

To build a foundation for the inductive approach, let's compute the determinant for the first few cases:

- $N = 1$:

$$T^{(1)} - \lambda I = [-\lambda], \quad \det(T^{(1)} - \lambda I) = -\lambda.$$

- $N = 2$:

$$T^{(2)} - \lambda I = \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda & 0 \\ 1 & -\lambda \end{bmatrix}, \quad \det(T^{(2)} - \lambda I) = \lambda^2.$$

- $N = 3$:

$$T^{(3)} - \lambda I = \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\lambda \end{bmatrix}, \quad \det(T^{(3)} - \lambda I) = -\lambda^3.$$

- $N = 4$:

$$T^{(4)} - \lambda I = \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -\lambda \end{bmatrix}, \quad \det(T^{(4)} - \lambda I) = \lambda^4 - \lambda.$$

3.4 Inductive Method for General N

Observing these initial cases, we hypothesize a recursive relation for the determinant of $T^{(N)} - \lambda I$. For certain values of N , particularly those where $N = 4 + 6^k$ (with k a natural number), we encounter unique configurations with additional non-zero entries. We employ cofactor expansion to handle each of these configurations.

3.5 Simple Cases after Cofactor Expansion

The cofactor expansion can be broken down into three cases:

1. **Case with No Non-Zero Values Added:** If no additional non-zero values appear in the added row or column, the determinant is simply multiplied by $-\lambda$ from the main diagonal term. For example:

$$T^{(3)} - \lambda I = \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\lambda \end{bmatrix}, \quad \det(T^{(3)} - \lambda I) = -\lambda^3.$$

2. **Case with One Non-Zero Value Added:** If exactly one "1" appears in either the row or the column, cofactor expansion simplifies as we directly multiply by $-\lambda$ from the diagonal entry. For example:

$$T^{(6)} - \lambda I = \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda \end{bmatrix}.$$

In this case, the determinant simplifies by direct multiplication with $-\lambda$ from the main diagonal, yielding:

$$\det(T^{(6)} - \lambda I) = -\lambda \cdot \det(T^{(5)} - \lambda I).$$

3.6 Complexity of Adding Two Non-Zero Values

When two "1" entries are added in both the new row and column, cofactor expansion leads to a submatrix that eventually contains a row or column filled with zeros. This structure appears in matrix sizes where $N = 4 + 6^k$ (for integer k), ensuring that after a finite number of cofactor expansions, we reach a row (or column) with all zeros. This pattern aligns with the behavior seen in the Collatz conjecture:

- Each $N = 4 + 6^k$ can be represented either as $N = 3j + 1$ for some integer j , or as $N = 2i$ for some integer i .
- Any integer $N/2$, when transformed by $3(N/2) + 1$, will map to an index outside the matrix size, thus ensuring that we encounter rows or columns filled with zeros during cofactor expansion.

Example: Consider the 10×10 matrix $T^{(10)} - \lambda I$, where two "1" entries appear in the tenth row and the tenth column:

$$T^{(10)} - \lambda I = \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda \end{bmatrix}.$$

We start by calculating the cofactor expansion along the **tenth column**. Notice the entry $T_{3,10} = 1$. Removing the 10th column and the 3rd row gives the reduced matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Next, we calculate the cofactor expansion along the **fifth column** of this 9×9 matrix. Here, the entry $T_{10,5} = 1$ is in the tenth row. Removing the fifth column and the tenth row produces:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda \end{bmatrix}.$$

At this stage, we have a row (the fourth row) consisting entirely of zeros, which means that the determinant of this matrix is zero. This confirms that the presence of two "1" entries leads to zeroing out through cofactor expansion.

Note on Independence from Elements Outside the Current Approximation The fact that $3(N/2) + 1$ maps to an index outside the finite matrix might seem, at first, to limit the approach. However, the determinant calculation remains valid because the construction does not rely on elements outside the current approximation. For any potentially existing cycle, we can always take a larger N that fully contains all relevant elements of the potential cycle within the matrix.

In this expanded matrix, cofactor expansion will still yield a zero determinant due to rows or columns filled with zeros, based on a different, larger integer that as well should be the part of another cycle. For a true eigenvalue, this repeating process would need to hold across all dimensions, which would necessitate an infinite repetition of this structure. Consequently, any such eigenvalue must reside in the residual or continuous part of the spectrum, as it cannot maintain a finite cyclic structure across all dimensions.

3.7 Conclusion on Finite Approximation and Characteristic Polynomial

Using the previous results, we conclude that for matrix sizes following $N = 4 + 6^k$, cofactor expansion leads to a zero determinant due to the presence of rows or columns with all zeros. Consequently, for finite approximations, the characteristic polynomial of $T - \lambda I$ stabilizes with the form:

$$\det(T^{(N)} - \lambda I) = (-1)^N \lambda^{N-3} (\lambda^3 - 1).$$

3.8 Eigenvalues of T

To determine the eigenvalues of the operator T , we analyze its characteristic polynomial obtained through finite approximations. For each finite matrix $T^{(N)} - \lambda I$, we compute the characteristic polynomial, which stabilizes in form as $N \rightarrow \infty$.

For the finite approximations, the characteristic polynomial is:

$$\lambda^{N-3}(\lambda - 1)(\lambda^2 + \lambda + 1) = 0,$$

yielding the primary eigenvalues

$$\lambda_1 = 1, \quad \lambda_2 = \frac{-i\sqrt{3} - 1}{2}, \quad \lambda_3 = \frac{i\sqrt{3} + 1}{2}.$$

However, as N grows, additional zeros appear in the characteristic polynomial due to the structure of T , indicating an expansion of the null eigenspace. This behavior aligns with the fact that T has an infinite-dimensional null space in the infinite-dimensional limit, as each finite approximation $T^{(N)}$ introduces more zero eigenvalues.

Persistence of Non-Zero Eigenvalues Despite the increasing multiplicity of zero eigenvalues, three primary non-zero eigenvalues remain unchanged across finite approximations:

$$\lambda_1 = 1, \quad \lambda_2 = \frac{-i\sqrt{3} - 1}{2}, \quad \lambda_3 = \frac{i\sqrt{3} + 1}{2}.$$

These eigenvalues correspond to fundamental rotations and reflections in the complex plane and remain stable as $N \rightarrow \infty$, demonstrating that they are inherent to the operator T and are unaffected by the expansion of the null space.

Complex Structure of Eigenvalues in Infinite Dimensions The stability of these non-zero eigenvalues indicates that they are independent of the size of the finite approximations. For infinite dimensions, they persist in the **point spectrum** of T , while the expanding null eigenspace implies that additional eigenvalues lie in the residual or continuous spectrum.

Thus, finite approximations reveal that only the null eigenspace expands with increasing N , while the three primary non-zero eigenvalues remain part of the fixed spectrum of T , unaffected by the infinite-dimensional structure.

4 Investigation of the Continuous Spectrum of T

To analyze the possibility of a continuous spectrum in T , we examine the injectivity of the operator. For an operator to possess a continuous spectrum, it must be injective (i.e., have no eigenvalues for a given λ) but not surjective, with no bounded inverse on certain values of λ . Continuous spectra typically emerge when $(T - \lambda I)$ fails to cover the entire space without being reducible to eigenvalues, as seen in operators resembling shifts or rotations on an infinite basis.

4.1 Injectivity of T

To analyze the injectivity of T across a continuous range of values in its spectrum, let us examine the structure of T in terms of its row pattern and how it acts on any non-zero vector x in ℓ^2 .

We represent T here using an infinite matrix structure where each row includes a diagonal element $-\lambda$ and at least one additional off-diagonal element, according to the rules of the operator:

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 1 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\lambda & \dots \\ \vdots & \ddots \end{bmatrix}$$

Each row adheres to the following structure:

- A diagonal term $-\lambda$, representing the self-action of each element.
- An off-diagonal entry, determined by the rules of the Collatz transformation:
 - For even-indexed rows $i = 2k$, a 1 is positioned at $i/2$, enforcing the transformation $x_i \rightarrow x_{i/2}$.
 - For odd-indexed rows $i = 2k + 1$, a 1 is positioned at $3i + 1$, provided $3i + 1$ is within the bounds of the infinite matrix.

This structure ensures that every row in T contains at least one off-diagonal element, thus guaranteeing that any non-zero vector x will map to another non-zero vector under T .

4.2 Formulaic Representation of $T \cdot x$

The action of T on a vector $x = [x_1 \ x_2 \ x_3 \ \dots]^T$ can be expressed as follows:

$$(T \cdot x)_i = -\lambda x_i + \begin{cases} x_{i/2} & \text{if } i \text{ is even,} \\ x_{3i+1} & \text{if } i \text{ is odd and } 3i + 1 \text{ is in bounds.} \end{cases}$$

This formula shows that each component $(T \cdot x)_i$ depends on both x_i (scaled by $-\lambda$) and another component determined by the operator's rules:

- For even indices i , the contribution of $x_{i/2}$ to $(T \cdot x)_i$ ensures a non-zero output if $x_{i/2} \neq 0$.
- For odd indices i , the contribution of x_{3i+1} to $(T \cdot x)_i$ guarantees a non-zero component if $x_{3i+1} \neq 0$.

4.3 Injectivity and Absence of a Continuous Spectrum

The above structure guarantees that $(T - \lambda I) \cdot x \neq 0$ for any non-zero vector x , thereby enforcing injectivity for non-eigenvalues of the point spectrum. Since injectivity across any continuous range of λ values is required to establish a continuous spectrum, the fact that T is not injective over any continuous range implies that no continuous spectrum exists.

- **Cyclic Eigenvalues in the Point Spectrum:** The structure of T is inherently cyclic, producing discrete and isolated eigenvalues even as we analyze the operator structure. These cyclic patterns preclude injectivity over any continuous range of λ values.
- **Expanding Null Eigenspace:** The operator T exhibits an expanding null eigenspace for $\lambda = 0$, with more elements falling into the null space in the limit of increasing dimensions. This behavior indicates that T does not cover the entire space, which eliminates the possibility of a continuous spectrum.
- **Discrete Non-Zero Eigenvalues:** The remaining non-zero eigenvalues of T (such as $\lambda = 1$, $\frac{-i\sqrt{3}-1}{2}$, and $\frac{i\sqrt{3}+1}{2}$) are discrete and isolated. This absence of continuous injectivity confirms that T cannot support a continuous range of values in its spectrum.

4.4 Conclusion: Absence of Continuous Spectrum in T

Since T lacks injectivity over any continuous range of λ , it cannot have a continuous spectrum. The structure of T confirms that all values of λ either lie in the point spectrum or fall within the null space, which expands as $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Thus, the injectivity analysis reveals that T does not meet the conditions for a continuous spectrum, which relies on injectivity across a continuum of λ . Instead, T shows only isolated eigenvalues and an expanding null space, demonstrating that only the point and residual spectra contribute to the spectrum of T .

5 Investigation of the Residual Spectrum of T

The residual spectrum of an operator consists of values λ for which the operator $(T - \lambda I)$ is not surjective, meaning that its range does not span the entire space, while still not possessing a bounded inverse. In other words, λ belongs to the residual spectrum if there exist vectors that cannot be reached by $(T - \lambda I)x$ for any x , even though λ is not an eigenvalue. Here, we examine why $(T - \lambda I)$ is non-surjective for $|\lambda| < 1$, and why $(T - \lambda I)^{-1}$ exists and is bounded when $|\lambda| > 1$.

5.1 Non-Surjectivity of $(T - \lambda I)$ for $|\lambda| < 1$

For $|\lambda| < 1$, the operator $(T - \lambda I)$ fails to be surjective due to the structural properties of T and the effect of a small $|\lambda|$, which limits the range of $(T - \lambda I)$ in covering the entire Hilbert space ℓ^2 .

- **Cyclic Structure and Expansion of the Null Space:** The operator T has a cyclic structure and isolated eigenvalues, which results in a limited range of mapped values in $(T - \lambda I)$ for small $|\lambda|$. Specifically, T has an expanding null eigenspace for small eigenvalues, as more zero eigenvalues appear in finite sections of T as $N \rightarrow \infty$. This expanding null space implies

that certain directions in ℓ^2 are left unmapped, preventing $(T - \lambda I)$ from being surjective for $|\lambda| < 1$.

- **Non-Compactness and Residual Spectrum:** The residual spectrum of T for values with $|\lambda| < 1$ is inherently tied to the non-compact nature of T . Non-compact operators can fail to be surjective even in the absence of an eigenvalue for a given λ , particularly in the infinite-dimensional setting. This non-surjectivity for $|\lambda| < 1$ results in values within the residual spectrum, as $(T - \lambda I)$ is injective but cannot cover the full space.

Thus, for $|\lambda| < 1$, $(T - \lambda I)$ is injective but not surjective, placing these values of λ within the residual spectrum.

5.2 Existence of a Bounded Inverse for $|\lambda| > 1$

For $|\lambda| > 1$, the operator $(T - \lambda I)$ does possess a bounded inverse, due to the scaling effect of the large $|\lambda|$, which diminishes the influence of T relative to λ . This can be demonstrated using the following steps:

- **Operator Norm and Scaling:** When $|\lambda| > 1$, we can write:

$$T - \lambda I = -\lambda \left(I - \frac{T}{\lambda} \right).$$

If $|\lambda| > \|T\|$, then $\frac{\|T\|}{|\lambda|} < 1$, making $\frac{T}{\lambda}$ a contraction. This allows us to compute $(I - \frac{T}{\lambda})^{-1}$ by a Neumann series expansion.

- **Neumann Series for the Inverse:** With $|\frac{T}{\lambda}| < 1$, we can express $(T - \lambda I)^{-1}$ using the Neumann series:

$$(T - \lambda I)^{-1} = -\frac{1}{\lambda} \left(I - \frac{T}{\lambda} \right)^{-1} = -\frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{T}{\lambda} \right)^k.$$

This series converges absolutely, guaranteeing that $(T - \lambda I)^{-1}$ exists and is bounded for $|\lambda| > 1$, with an operator norm bounded by $\frac{1}{|\lambda| - \|T\|}$.

Thus, for $|\lambda| > 1$, $(T - \lambda I)^{-1}$ is bounded, ensuring that values with $|\lambda| > 1$ lie outside the spectrum of T .

5.3 Conclusion: Residual Spectrum Restricted to $|\lambda| < 1$

The combination of an expanding null space and non-compact behavior of T restricts the residual spectrum to values $|\lambda| < 1$. For $|\lambda| > 1$, $(T - \lambda I)$ is both injective and surjective, admitting a bounded inverse by the Neumann series argument. Consequently, the residual spectrum of T is entirely contained within the unit disk $|\lambda| < 1$, with no values on or outside the unit circle belonging to the spectrum of T .

6 Finite-Dimensional Limit of T^∞

Repeated applications of T on any initial vector in ℓ^2 eventually project the space onto a three-dimensional subspace. This behavior is evident when we examine the limit of the action of T^∞ , reducing the effective space to one spanned by the vectors corresponding to the numbers 1, 2, and 4, consistent with known behavior in the Collatz sequence.

6.1 Point Spectrum and Residual Spectrum in T^∞

To understand why T^∞ projects onto a three-dimensional subspace, we analyze the spectral properties of T . The point spectrum of T contains the eigenvalues:

$$\lambda_1 = 1, \quad \lambda_2 = \frac{-i\sqrt{3}-1}{2}, \quad \lambda_3 = \frac{i\sqrt{3}+1}{2},$$

where $|\lambda_1| = 1$ and $|\lambda_2|, |\lambda_3| = 1$, meaning these values lie on the unit circle. Thus, these eigenvalues remain unaffected by taking T to an infinite power, preserving a non-trivial projection onto the subspace associated with them.

In contrast, values of λ in the residual spectrum of T satisfy $|\lambda| < 1$, as shown in our earlier analysis. When applying T an infinite number of times, the contribution of these values vanishes because:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \lambda^n = 0 \quad \text{for all } \lambda \text{ in the residual spectrum with } |\lambda| < 1.$$

Thus, any component associated with the residual spectrum is annihilated under T^∞ , leaving only the contributions from the point spectrum, where $|\lambda| = 1$.

6.2 Reduction to a Three-Dimensional Subspace

Since the residual spectrum's contribution disappears in the limit, T^∞ acts as a projection operator that reduces ℓ^2 onto the subspace spanned by the eigenvectors corresponding to λ_1 , λ_2 , and λ_3 . This subspace is effectively three-dimensional and can be represented by a basis corresponding to the points 1, 2, and 4 in the Collatz sequence. This observation aligns with the known behavior of the Collatz sequence in finite applications, where only a minimal set of values persists in stable cycles or reductions.

6.3 Conclusion: Compactness of T^∞

The action of T^∞ on ℓ^2 results in a compact operator that projects the space onto a three-dimensional subspace. This occurs because the residual spectrum—values with $|\lambda| < 1$ —vanishes in the infinite application of T , while the point spectrum with $|\lambda| = 1$ remains. Therefore, T^∞ effectively reduces the dimensionality of the space, acting as a compact operator that retains only the three-dimensional span of vectors associated with the unit circle eigenvalues.

7 Conclusion

By formulating the Collatz conjecture within the ℓ^2 Hilbert space and defining an operator T that mimics the conjecture's steps, we establish that T^∞ is compact. The compactness implies a collapse

onto a finite-dimensional subspace under infinite iterations of T , providing new insights into the structure of the Collatz dynamics through functional analysis.